

WASTE TO WEALTH: SUPER HARD CARBON MICROTUBE DERIVED FROM COTTON WASTE FOR COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The development of high performance, sustainable and inexpensive filler for composite applications is a highly innovative and promising approach to meet the increasing demands from society on wide range of applications. Carbon microtube (CMT) synthesized from cotton waste was successfully developed by direct pyrolysis of cotton waste in argon atmosphere. To make a comparison with other type of carbonaceous structures, two type of carbon materials including synthesized carbon microtubes (CMT) and carbon nanotube (CNT) were used for fabrication of titanium laminate composite via spark plasma sintering technique. A significant improvement in bending strength (1273 ± 11 MPa) and hardness (537 ± 28 Vickers) of Ti-CMT composites was observed compared to titanium laminate and Ti-CNT composite. Given the repeatability, high reinforcing performance and cost effectiveness of the cotton based carbon microtubes when compared to other well-known fillers such as carbon nanotubes, the carbon microtubes demonstrated great potential as low-cost, sustainable and effective filler for composite applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The way we used the textiles need to be fundamentally changed. A circular economy is an alternative to a traditional economy (fabrication, use and dispose) in which we keep resources in a loop for as much time as possible, try to maintain their value whilst in use, and repurpose for generating of new products at the end of utilization. [1, 2]. More than two thirds of the textile goes to landfill at the end of their use and just around 15% are recycled. Various scientific studies confirm that the disposal nature of fast fashion and throwaway culture is resulting a serious environmental, health, social and economic problems[3]. A sustainable and green economy can be achieved only by rethinking about industrial and environmental processes to optimize the use of waste materials and low cost resources. There is a raising awareness that current material consumption and reuse is not environmental friendly and sustainable[4]. Also the cost of synthetic materials have a big impact on developing cost effective product with enhanced mechanical and physical properties. This requires the developing of new techniques for using of recycled, waste or cheap materials in an economical way[2, 3]. The design of low-cost and high-performance materials for composite application is the key to promote their future commercialization.

Composites are enjoying increased interest in academia as well as industry due to combined advantages of at least the two different materials used to form hybrid structures for different applications including automotive, military and aerospace [5-8]. Different carbon based materials e.g. carbon fiber, fullerene, graphene and graphene oxide and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been successfully used in composite applications [9-12]. Carbon nanotubes superior physical, electrical, mechanical, optical, and thermal properties along with large surface area and porosity, chemical inertness, great volume to mass ratio and strong affinity towards pollutants make them the most studied material nowadays ; However due to the high cost of CNTs, development of alternative low-cost carbonaceous structure for composite application needs to be explored. The use of waste or recycled materials for fabrication of high performance filler remains a major challenge due to difficulty in fabrication process, and the high portion of impurity in material. Various precursors have been used for fabrication of carbon based filler, however the use of waste cotton for composite

application in the form of carbonized carbon is not reported yet.

2 IMPORTANCE OF TEXTILE WASTE RECYCLING

Disposal nature of fast fashion and throwaway culture is resulting a serious environmental, social and economic problems. In the last two decades not only the textile industry has doubled the production but also an average global annual consumption of textiles has doubled (from 7 to 13 kg per person) [13, 14].

According to Australia Bureau Statistics, 501,000 tonnes of textiles and leather sent to landfill in Australia alone in 2009-10, which means an average of 22.7kg per person [15], which is twice the global rate.

Figure 1 shows the textile waste management in USA since 1960[9]. In 2015, 16,030 thousands of tons of textile waste was generated, according to American Apparel and Footwear Association (EPA) only 15.28% of this amount has been recycled; 19.03% incinerated for energy recovery and the rest 65.69% have been discarded to landfill (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Textile waste management in USA 1960-2015. adapted from EPA data [16]

Figure 2 : Textile waste generation in USA 1960-2015. adapted from EPA data [16]

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Carbon microtubes (CMT) derived from cotton waste were prepared by the direct pyrolysis of cotton bundles from packaging industry. The cotton firstly washed with ethanol and deionized water and dried overnight. Then cotton samples were placed in a carbolite tube furnace under Argon flow to reach the carbonization temperature. The carbonization temperatures was 1300 °C[5]. The sintering process was performed using SPS machine in vacuum condition (20–25 Pa) with initial and final pressure of 10 and 50 MPa (applied at 1200 °C and continuously increasing in two stages by 20 MPa increments) at 1250 °C and 5 min soaking time.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Structural imaging of the carbon microtubes derived from cotton waste have been provided in figure 3. It is clearly seen that the carbon microtubes retained their tube shape and their size are between 3-7 μm . Ti-CMT and Ti-CNT laminated composite with TiC interfacial bond have been prepared successfully with spark plasma sintering method (Fig.4). Ti-CMT composite exhibited intergranular fracture of the TiC phase along the TiC-TiC boundaries and transgranular fracture through the CMTs fracture mechanism. While, the Ti-CNT composite showed so many dimples due to formation TiC nano wires at the separated layers which indicated ductile fracture behavior and poor bonding of layers.

Figure 3: SEM imaging of carbon microtubes derived from cotton waste in different magnifications

Figure 4: Schematic of laminated composite preparation and proposed bonding mechanism of layers

The mechanical properties examination demonstrate higher amounts of bending strength (1273 ± 11 MPa) and hardness (537 ± 28 Vickers) for cotton waste derived carbon microtube reinforced titanium compared to CNT reinforced Titanium composite[5]. Considering to the calculated amounts, both of Ti-CNT and Ti-CMT composites had relative density up to 99% [5].

The higher bending strength and hardness were obtained by Ti-CMT rather than Ti-CNT composite which can be as result of higher amounts of produced TiC and proper bonding of layers to each others. The little higher amounts of hardness for Ti-CMT can be assumed as higher carbon diffusion in surface layer due to mentioned above possibilities. The proposed fracture mechanisms of Ti-CNT and Ti-CMT composite have been illustrated at Fig. 5[5]. Formation TiC interfacial products were occurred in two state including reaction Ti with CNTs to form TiC nano wires for Ti-CNT composite and formation TiC carbide phase around CMTs with some of un-reacted CMTs for Ti-CMT sample. After applying stress on the specimens the included fracture mechanism of Ti-CNT sample is separation layers with remained dimples due to pulling out of TiC nano wire. On the other hand, the Ti-CMT composite shows crack propagation into both of formed TiC boundaries and un-reacted CMTs with creation many microcracks[5].

Figure 5: TiC formation and fracture mechanism of Ti-CNT and Ti-CMT composites during fracture.

5 CONCLUSIONS

An easy to apply one step method has been successfully developed to fabricate a carbon microtube from waste cotton to be used as a highly effective reinforcement material. Based on the higher mechanical property of the Ti-CMT compared with Ti-CNT that being processed through spark plasma sintering method, it is believed that there is a huge opportunity to use carbon microtube instead of other carbonaceous filler in composites. Given the repeatability, high reinforcing performance and cost effectiveness of the cotton based carbon microtubes when compared to other well-known fillers such as carbon nanotubes, the carbon microtubes demonstrated great potential as low-cost, sustainable and effective filler for composite applications.

REFERENCES

1. Haule, L.V., C.M. Carr, and M. Rigout, Preparation and physical properties of regenerated cellulose fibres from cotton waste garments. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2016. **112**: p. 4445-4451.
2. <https://fashionunited.com/global-fashion-industry-statistics/>.
3. Liu, W., et al., Eco-friendly post-consumer cotton waste recycling for regenerated cellulose fibers. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 2019. **206**: p. 141-148.
4. Briga-Sá, A., et al., Textile waste as an alternative thermal insulation building material solution. *Construction and Building Materials*. Elsevier, 2013. **38**: p. 155-160.
5. Shirvanimoghaddam, K., et al., Super hard carbon microtubes derived from natural cotton for development of high performance titanium composites. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 2019. **775**: p. 601-616.
6. Todor, M.P., et al., Researches on the development of new composite materials complete / partially biodegradable using natural textile fibers of new vegetable origin and those recovered

- from textile waste, in *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 2017, IOP Publication.
7. Echeverria, C.A., et al., Cascading use of textile waste for the advancement of fibre reinforced composites for building applications. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Elsevier, 2019. **208** p. 1524e1536.
 8. Naebe, M. and K. Shirvanimoghaddam, Functionally graded materials: A review of fabrication and properties. *Applied Materials Today*, 2016. **5**: p. 223-245.
 9. Shirvanimoghaddam, K., et al., Carbon fiber reinforced metal matrix composites: Fabrication processes and properties. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2017. **92**: p. 70-96.
 10. Kumar, N., H.C. Chittappa, and S. Ezhil Vannan, Development of Aluminium-Nickel Coated Short Carbon Fiber Metal Matrix Composites. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2018. **5**(5, Part 2): p. 11336-11345.
 11. Isaza Merino, C.A., et al., Metal matrix composites reinforced with carbon nanotubes by an alternative technique. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 2017. **707**: p. 257-263.
 12. De Volder, M.F.L., et al., *Carbon Nanotubes: Present and Future Commercial Applications*. 2013. **339**(6119): p. 535-539.
 13. Milburn, J. Aussies send 85% of textiles to landfill. 2016.
 14. Souchet, F., Fashion has a huge waste problem. Here's how it can change. 2019, World Economic Forum: Online: <https://www.weforum.org>.
 15. statistics, A.B.o. 4655.0.55.002 - Information Paper: Towards the Australian Environmental-Economic Accounts. Chapter 4 Waste. 2013.
 16. EPA. Textiles: Material-Specific Data. 2017.